

Rethinking Organizational Effectiveness: Exploring the Buffering Roles of Positive Affectivity and Task Characteristics in the Associations of Career Growth Opportunity, Perceived Supervisor Support and Prosocial Behaviour among Nurses

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Abstract

The increasing demands and challenges in the healthcare industry, particularly within the nursing profession, necessitate a deeper understanding of the factors that enhance nurses' motivation to engage in prosocial motivation behaviors. This study examines the pivotal issue of how positive affectivity and task characteristics buffer the relationship between career growth opportunity and perceived supervisor support on prosocial motivation behavior among nurses. This study employed a transverse research design involving 750 nurses aged 29–55 years ($M = 35.17$, $SD = 7.48$) selected from government-owned hospitals in Southeast Nigeria. Data were collected via an online survey utilizing standardized measures, including the Career Growth Opportunity Scale, Perceived Supervisor Support Scale, Positive Affective Scale, Task Characteristics Scale, and the Prosocial Motivation Scale. Hayes Process Macro, Model 2, version 3 was used for data analysis. The findings indicate that career growth opportunities, perceived supervisor support, positive affectivity, and task characteristics have a positive relationship with prosocial motivation behavior. In addition, positive affectivity moderated the relationship between organizational career growth and prosocial motivation behaviour, but did not on perceived supervisor support and prosocial motivation behaviour. However, task characteristics moderated the extent to which career growth opportunity and supervisor support predicted prosocial motivation behavior. These results highlight the importance of fostering a supportive work environment and enhancing job characteristics to promote prosocial motivation behaviors, which are crucial for improving patient care and team dynamics in healthcare. The implications of this study suggest that healthcare organizations should consider individual psychological traits and job design when developing strategies aimed at enhancing employee engagement and supportive workplace behaviors.

Keywords: *Career Growth Opportunity, Perceived Supervisor Support, Positive Affectivity, Prosocial Motivation Behaviour.*

INTRODUCTION

Nurses play an indispensable role in delivering essential services, often in high-pressure environments because they constitute the largest workforce segment, providing direct patient care, managing treatment plans, and responding to medical emergencies (Ike et al., 2024; Nnadozie et al., 2025; Oldenmenger et al., 2024). Their role became particularly evident during the COVID-19 pandemic, highlighting their resilience and the challenges they faced, such as workforce shortages, burnout, and mental health struggles (Jatt et al., 2025). Globally, nurses are at the forefront of healthcare delivery, ensuring quality patient care while working in

increasingly difficult conditions (Ike et al., 2025). Many countries are experiencing a nursing workforce crisis due to high turnover rates, insufficient recruitment, and the migration of skilled professionals to more developed healthcare systems (Ghimire & Neupane, 2025). The global nursing shortage is particularly severe in low- and middle-income countries, where resource constraints and lack of investment in healthcare infrastructure continue to impact workforce sustainability (Ablaza et al., 2025). Despite these challenges, Nigerian nurses continue to play a crucial role in frontline health care service delivery. However, without urgent reforms to address career growth opportunities, workplace safety, professional recognition, counterproductive work behaviors, and job dissatisfaction are likely to persist (Aggarwal et al. 2024). Addressing these concerns requires a multi-stakeholder approach involving government agencies, healthcare institutions, and international health organizations to improve nurses' retention and overall healthcare system efficiency.

However, the contemporary landscape of organizational behavior, particularly within the healthcare sector, is increasingly characterized by an emphasis on employee well-being and performance outcomes influenced by psychological factors such as prosocial motivation behavior (Linwei et al., 2023; Snipp et al., 2017). This is pertinent because nurses frequently encounter high-stress environments, often exacerbated by issues such as staffing shortages and heightened patient demands, making the understanding of prosocial motivation behavior nuances critical. Prosocial motivation behavior fosters actions intended to benefit others, is essential for enhancing patient care and fostering a supportive workplace atmosphere (Schroeder & Graziano, 2015). Prosocial motivation behaviour refers to voluntary actions intended to benefit or improve the well-being of another individual or group, encompassing activities such as helping, sharing, comforting, cooperating, and protecting others. It plays a vital role in improving patient outcomes, fostering a collaborative work environment, and ultimately enhancing the efficiency of healthcare organizations (Grant & Berg, 2021). In healthcare industry, particularly among nurses, prosocial motivation behaviour plays a crucial role in fostering compassionate patient care, teamwork, and overall organizational effectiveness. Given the frontline nature of nursing, nurses' ability and motivation to engage in prosocial motivation behaviors are essential for maintaining patient well-being, ensuring safety, and promoting positive organizational outcomes. A high level of prosocial motivation behaviour among nurses is linked to improved patient-centered care, reduced medical errors, and increased job satisfaction, all of which contribute to better organizational performance (Bolino & Grant, 2016). Hence, the importance of prosocial motivation behaviour in the healthcare sector is underscored by the increasing complexity of patient care and necessity for interdisciplinary collaboration. Research has shown that nurses with strong prosocial motivation behavior are more likely to display altruistic behaviors, contribute to a supportive team culture, and exhibit heightened commitment to patient care (Kwan & Mao, 2020).

However, the focus on Nigerian nurses in the southeastern region holds both contextual and theoretical importance for comprehending prosocial motivation behavior within healthcare environments. Nursing, as a profession centered on assistance, inherently requires empathy, cooperation, and altruism—fundamental aspects of prosocial behavior. However, the degree to which these behaviors are manifested and maintained is significantly affected by organizational, cultural, and socio-economic conditions. The healthcare context in southeastern Nigeria offers a unique setting for analyzing these dynamics. First, the region's healthcare system is characterized by resource constraints, heavy workloads, and systemic challenges such as inadequate staffing, low remuneration, and insufficient institutional support (Okoye et al., 2021; Onan, 2025). These contextual stressors create a challenging work environment that tests

the limits of nurses' willingness to engage in prosocial actions beyond formal job requirements. Thus, investigating prosocial motivation behavior under these conditions can elucidate the mechanisms through which supportive organizational factors—such as perceived supervisor support and career growth opportunity foster or sustain helping behaviors in high-strain contexts. Secondly, the sociocultural fabric of the area and Nigeria more broadly provides a compelling perspective for exploring prosocial motivation behavior. This is because extant studies in Nigeria demonstrate that self-compassion, empathic concern, emotional intelligence, and well-being are linked to prosocial tendencies (Emmanuel & Olaseni, 2020; Obi et al., 2023). These findings suggest that indigenous values of interdependence and reciprocity may shape workplace helping and citizenship behaviors. Aligning with the above postulation, the Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964) offers a theoretical framework for understanding how reciprocal social relationships within organizations drive voluntary and extra-role behaviors (Liaquat & Mehmood, 2017). Thus, focusing on Nigerian nurses in southeast region addresses an empirical gap in the literature, because research on prosocial motivation behavior and organizational citizenship behavior among African healthcare workers (e.g., Nigeria) is limited (e.g., Owoicho et al., 2023). Hence, this study contributes to the contextual diversification of prosocial motivation behavior research and enhances the external validity of current frameworks, which are largely derived from Western and Asian contexts. This focus has practical and policy relevance, because understanding the factors that promote or hinder prosocial motivation behavior among nurses can inform management practices and policy interventions aimed at strengthening teamwork, job satisfaction, and patient care quality, which are key priorities for improving healthcare delivery in Nigeria. Hence, examining prosocial motivation behavior among nurses in the southeast region is both contextually and theoretically significant because it provides an opportunity to explore how socio-organizational conditions, cultural values, and individual dispositions interact to shape prosocial tendencies in a high-demand profession, while simultaneously enriching global discourse on prosocial behavior in diverse cultural and economic contexts.

This is pertinent because prosocial motivation behaviour in nursing is not only beneficial for patients and healthcare institutions, but also for the nurses themselves. For instance, studies indicate that prosocial motivated nurses experience higher job satisfaction, lower burnout rates, and a stronger sense of professional purpose (Shin et al., 2021). These positive outcomes suggest that fostering a workplace environment that encourages prosocial motivation can be an effective strategy for healthcare organizations seeking to improve both employee retention and quality of patient care.

In the context of organizational behavior, prosocial motivation behaviour differs from related constructs such as organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) and altruism. While OCB refers to discretionary workplace behaviors that benefit the organization but are not explicitly rewarded, altruism denotes a selfless concern for others without expectation of personal gain. Prosocial motivation behaviour specifically pertains to the internal drive that compels individuals to engage in acts of kindness and support within the workplace, without anticipation of reward (Bolino & Grant, 2016). Unlike OCB, which is often linked to reciprocity and organizational expectations, prosocial motivation behaviour is primarily self-initiated and stems from a genuine desire to positively impact others (Hu & Liden, 2015). Such prosocial motivation behavior can manifest in the form of task-focused prosocial motivation, where employees engage in extra-role behaviors that enhance task performance, such as mentoring colleagues or improving workflow efficiency (Grant & Mayer, 2009), or relational prosocial motivation, which emphasizes interpersonal connections and support, such as emotional

assistance to colleagues or patients in distress (Shin et al., 2021). In nursing, both dimensions are highly relevant, as nurses frequently demonstrate prosocial motivation by providing emotional reassurance to patients, assisting co-workers in high-stress situations, and actively participating in organizational initiatives aimed at improving patient care.

Furthermore, these behaviors do not occur in isolation; they are influenced by many factors including career growth opportunity and perceived supervisor support. Career growth opportunity refer to the perceived availability of advancement, skill development, and professional learning within an organization. In nursing, career growth opportunity encompasses promotion pathways, specialized training programs, mentorship, and opportunities for role expansion (Atalla et al., 2024). Nurses who perceive clear career progression tend to be more engaged, committed, and motivated to contribute positively to their workplaces (Cheng et al., 2020). Career growth opportunity not only provide a sense of job security and professional fulfillment, but also influence nurses' willingness to engage in organizational prosocial motivation behaviors, such as mentoring colleagues and improving patient care initiatives (Dill et al., 2016). Studies (e.g. Chen et al., 2025; Giang, 2024; Nagi Ali et al., 2024) has demonstrated that nurses who perceive clearer career growth opportunity tend to be more engaged, committed, and motivated to contribute positively in their workplace. This indicates that perceived career growth opportunity among employees facilitate prosocial motivation behaviors because of the inherent sense of belonging identified within their work setting. This suggests that career growth opportunity foster prosocial motivation behavior among organizational members. Invariably, career growth opportunity is conceptualized through two dimensions: vertical and horizontal development. Vertical growth refers to promotions, leadership roles, and increased responsibilities, whereas horizontal growth involves skill enhancement, cross-training, and specialization (Lagarde & Blaauw, 2013). Both forms of development opportunities contribute to nurses' intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, reinforcing their commitment to organizational goals. For instance, when career growth opportunities are evident, nurses are more likely to feel empowered and motivated to engage in discretionary helping behaviors, strengthening workplace cohesion and patient care quality (Ong et al., 2019). Research indicates that when individuals perceive opportunities for career advancement, they often demonstrate elevated levels of prosocial motivation behavior motivated by intrinsic factors and a sense of belonging to their workplace community (Feather et al., 2018; Linwei et al., 2023).

However, this relationship is further enhanced by perceived supervisor support, which is a critical factor in fostering a positive work environment. Studies suggest that supportive supervision not only increases employee satisfaction but also cultivates a culture in which prosocial motivation behaviors are encouraged and rewarded (Barik et al., 2025). Perceived supervisor support refers to employees' belief that their supervisors value their contributions, provide assistance, and care about their well-being (Wanyama et al., 2025). In nursing, where workplace demands are high and emotional labour is significant, supportive supervisors play a crucial role in shaping job satisfaction, resilience, and engagement in prosocial motivation behaviours (Abed El Aziz et al., 2024). Supervisor support is not merely about offering guidance; it involves emotional encouragement, professional development opportunities, and advocacy for employee needs (Arshad et al., 2021). Thus, nurses who feel supported by their supervisors tend to experience greater motivation, lower burnout, and higher levels of commitment to their organizations. The nature of the nursing profession makes supervisory relationships important in shaping workplace motivation. Nurses operate in high-stress environments, where patient safety, emotional strain, and workload intensity create constant

challenges. A supportive supervisor provides clear direction, emotional reassurance, and advocacy for resources, allowing nurses to focus on delivering high-quality patient care without excessive stress (Abdelmotaleb & Metwally, 2022).

Studies (e.g., Ng et al., 2023) have shown that nurses with strong supervisory support report higher job satisfaction, lower stress levels, and greater willingness to assist colleagues and patients. Conversely, perceived lack of supervisor support is linked to burnout, emotional exhaustion, and reduced engagement in prosocial behaviors (Özkara et al., 2022). Supervisory support also influences nurse retention, as employees who feel undervalued by their managers are more likely to leave their jobs in search of better work environments that foster recognition and support (Frazier & Tupper 2018). This is pertinent because perceived supervisor support fosters organizational prosocial motivation behaviours by creating a trust-based work environment in which nurses feel valued and empowered to go beyond their formal job responsibilities. Supportive supervisors encourage collaboration, recognize employee efforts, and provide constructive feedback, all of which reinforce a culture of discretionary helping behaviors (Abed El Aziz et al., 2024).

Furthermore, in the evolving landscape of modern work environments, particularly among nurses, who constitute the foundation of service delivery, comprehending the complex interaction between psychological factors and organizational dynamics is increasingly crucial. Recent evidence underscores the significant role of positive affectivity, defined as the degree to which individuals experience positive moods and emotions, in shaping not only individual well-being but also behavioral outcomes within the workplace (Naragon-Gainey & Watson, 2019). As discourse has progressed, researchers have increasingly highlighted the significance of personal attributes, such as positive affectivity, in influencing the outcomes of supervisor support and career advancement opportunities. For example, Yoon and Thye (2000) identified that individuals exhibiting high levels of positive affectivity are more inclined to perceive supervisor support as authentic, thereby enhancing their engagement in prosocial behaviors. Evidence indicates that positive affectivity not only enhances individual well-being, but also plays a crucial role in influencing prosocial behavior within workplace dynamics (George, 1991). Thus, nurses exhibiting high levels of positive affectivity are more inclined to perceive their supervisors' support as authentic, thereby fostering an environment conducive to cooperative and helpful workplace interactions. This alignment between perceived support and emotional states underscores the interplay between individual psychological factors and organizational dynamics.

On the other hand, task characteristics is another factor that can influence the interaction between the antecedent and outcome variable. Task characteristics refer to the inherent attributes of a job that influence how employees perceive, approach, and perform their work (Grobelsna, 2019). These characteristics include task variety, autonomy, task significance, skill utilization, and feedback mechanisms, all of which shape employees' motivation, job satisfaction, and engagement in discretionary behaviours (Grant & Sonnentag, 2010). Task characteristics play a pivotal role in determining the extent to which nurses experience their work as meaningful, challenging, and rewarding. For instance, when nurses perceive their tasks as significant and engaging, they are more likely to display higher levels of prosocial motivation and discretionary helping behaviours (Bellé, 2014). For instance, task characteristics such as task significance and autonomy have been demonstrated to have a direct impact on employee motivation and behavior, indicating that the nature of a job can either promote or hinder prosocial tendencies (Cotič et al., 2025). This relationship is further

reinforced by perspectives rooted in the Job Characteristics Model, which posits that empowering job designs can enhance an employee's sense of fulfilment and willingness to engage in supportive actions towards colleagues (Chanie et al., 2023)

Drawing upon Social Exchange Theory (SET; Blau, 1964), the proximal relationships between positive affectivity and task characteristics on career growth opportunity, perceived supervisor support, and prosocial motivation behaviour can be explained as reciprocal exchanges between employees and their work environment. SET posits that social behaviour is the result of an exchange process in which individuals seek to maximize benefits and minimize costs. When employees perceive that their organization or supervisor provides valuable socioemotional and developmental resources—such as opportunities for career advancement and supportive supervision—they interpret these as indicators of organizational investment and trust. In line with the norm of reciprocity, employees feel obliged to reciprocate through discretionary, positive actions that benefit others and the organization, such as prosocial motivation behaviours.

However, the strength of these exchange-based relationships may vary depending on individual dispositions and contextual factors. Thus, positive affectivity serves as an important individual-level moderator that shapes how employees interpret and respond to social exchanges. Employees with high positive affectivity are predisposed to experience positive emotions and view work-related interactions more favourably. From an SET perspective, they are more likely to perceive career growth opportunities and supervisor support as genuine organizational investments, thereby experiencing stronger feelings of obligation to reciprocate through prosocial motivation behaviours. In contrast, employees with low positive affectivity may interpret the same exchanges less positively, diminishing the motivational force of reciprocity.

Similarly, task characteristics represent a contextual moderator that influences the translation of social exchange perceptions into behaviour. When employees work in enriched task environments—characterized by autonomy, task variety, significance, and feedback—they experience their roles as meaningful and perceive organizational support as consistent with their work reality. Such alignment strengthens the quality of the exchange relationship and enhances the likelihood that employees will reciprocate through prosocial motivation behaviour. Conversely, when task characteristics are poor or restrictive, employees may perceive a mismatch between supportive gestures and their actual work experience, weakening the perceived fairness and reciprocity of the exchange behaviour.

Furthermore, the growing acknowledgment of the influence of psychological and contextual factors on employee behavior highlights the intricate nature of workplace dynamics, particularly among nurses, who frequently operate in challenging environments (Sims et al., 2022). While extensive research has established a direct connection between antecedent and outcome variables, a notable gap persists in comprehending how this relationship interacts with positive affectivity and task characteristics to affect prosocial behavior. Interestingly, the moderating roles of positive affectivity and task characteristics are crucial in this dynamic relationship. This is pertinent because positive affectivity is linked to enhanced emotional states, which can augment the motivational effects of career growth opportunity and supervisory support (Fredrick & Branigan, 2005). Thus, employees with high levels of positive affect are more inclined to engage in prosocial behaviors as they approach their roles with enthusiasm, thereby reinforcing the notion that individual emotional states can significantly influence workplace interactions. Invariably, task characteristics (autonomy, skill variety, task

identity and task significance) have been identified as critical moderator influencing employees' perceptions of career growth opportunities and supervisory support (Cotič et al., 2025). Tasks designed to be engaging can enhance the likelihood that employees perceive their contributions as impactful, thereby fostering increased prosocial engagement (Carlo et al., 2019). The interaction between these psychological and task-related factors offers a comprehensive understanding of employee behavior, underscoring the importance of both individual attributes and workplace environments in promoting positive outcomes. The proximal influence of task characteristics may further moderate these relationships by determining the extent to which nurses feel empowered and engaged in their roles. This is because task characteristics connote the inherent attributes of a job that influence how employees perceive, approach, and perform their work (Gobelna 2019). These characteristics include task variety, autonomy, task significance, skill utilization, and feedback mechanisms, all of which shape employees' motivation, job satisfaction, and engagement in discretionary behaviours (Grant & Sonnentag, 2010). In nursing, task characteristics play a pivotal role in determining the extent to which nurses experience their work as meaningful, challenging, and rewarding. For instance, when nurses perceive their tasks as significant and engaging, they are more likely to display higher levels of prosocial motivation and discretionary helping behaviours (Bellé, 2014). Understanding these dynamics is not only of academic significance but also has practical implications. As organizations increasingly prioritize employee engagement and retention, identifying the psychological mechanisms influencing prosocial motivation behavior can facilitate targeted interventions in workplace policies and practices.

In reviewing the current body of knowledge, it is evident that positive emotions, coupled with supportive workplace relationships, are pivotal components in the broader discourse on employee development and social behavior within organizational settings. Nevertheless, adopting an integrated approach that incorporates task characteristics and psychological variables such as positive affectivity will yield a more holistic understanding of individual and organizational outcomes. In light of this context, the primary aim of this study is to empirically investigate the moderating roles of positive affectivity, defined as an individual's general propensity to experience positive moods, and task characteristics, such as job demands and task significance, in influencing the relationships between career growth opportunity and perceived supervisor support on prosocial motivation behavior. By examining these moderating roles, this study seeks to underscore the existing empirical findings while laying the groundwork for future research that could inform effective strategies for enhancing the well-being and performance of nurses, thereby addressing the significant gaps identified. In addition, this study sought to elucidate these complex interactions and determine the conditions under which supportive workplace environments may foster enhanced prosocial outcomes. This insight will provide a nuanced understanding of how individual and task factors interact to inform nurses behaviors in dynamic healthcare settings by aiming to enhance both individual well-being and organizational effectiveness.

The Current Research

Adopting Social Exchange Theory (Homans, 1958), we sought a deeper comprehension of the multifaceted interrelations among career growth opportunities, perceived supervisor support, positive affectivity, task characteristics, and prosocial behavior among frontline workers in Nigeria. The theory posits that relationships are formed and maintained through reciprocal exchanges of tangible or intangible resources between individuals and organizations.

When employees perceive favorable treatment, they feel obligated to reciprocate through positive attitudes and behaviors. This provides a robust framework for understanding how frontline workers' perceptions of support, empowerment, and opportunity shape their willingness to go beyond formal duties. These reciprocal dynamics are key to sustaining high-performance collaborative frontline teams in service-intensive environments. This invariably elucidates how perceived supervisor support can enhance the beneficial effects of affectivity on employee behavior, thereby promoting a work environment that supports assistance and collaboration.

The relationship between career growth opportunities, perceived supervisor support, and prosocial behavior among frontline workers has received attention in recent scholarly literature (Naragon-Gainey & Watson, 2019; Ni & Hung, 2025; Okurame, 2012; Todd & Kent, 2006; Schroeder & Graziano, 2015), although in an isolated form among these variables of interest. Initial studies predominantly concentrated on the direct effects of perceived supervisor support and career growth opportunities, highlighting their crucial role in enhancing job satisfaction and organizational commitment. These studies have facilitated subsequent investigations into the complex interplay of positive affectivity, task characteristics, and their moderating effects on this dynamic. Thus, there is a notable gap in the literature regarding the interaction between psychological factors (e.g., positive affectivity) and tangible task characteristics in shaping career growth opportunities and perceived extent of supervisor support.

The interaction between positive affectivity, task characteristics, and their impact on career advancement opportunities and perceived supervisor support constitutes a significant area of investigation in the academic literature. Current research (e.g., Gherghel et al., 2020; Naragon-Gainey & Watson, 2019) underscores the significance of positive affectivity, which is associated with improved job performance and prosocial behaviors among employees, particularly those in frontline positions (e.g., nurses) who frequently work under considerable pressure. However, these studies often isolate the under-study of these variables, lacking a comprehensive model that captures the multifaceted experiences of frontline workers. Invariably, the interaction of these elements may vary significantly based on individual characteristics, particularly positive affectivity and task characteristics.

However, grounded in the principles of Social Exchange Theory (SET), the proposed conceptual model posits that employees' perceptions of career growth opportunity and perceived supervisor support function as pivotal antecedents of prosocial motivation behavior. These variables embody forms of socioemotional and developmental investment from the organization and supervisors, which engender a sense of obligation among employees to reciprocate through voluntary and helping-oriented behaviors that benefit others and the organization.

Nevertheless, the proposed model asserts that these exchange-based relationships are not uniform across all individuals or work environments. Specifically, positive affectivity and task characteristics are proposed as moderators that influence the strength of these relationships. This is pertinent because employees with high positive affectivity are more inclined to perceive career growth opportunity and perceived supervisor support as genuine and rewarding exchanges, thereby exhibiting stronger prosocial tendencies. Similarly, when task characteristics—such as autonomy, task significance, and feedback—are pronounced, employees perceive a more meaningful and consistent work environment, reinforcing the reciprocity mechanism that drives prosocial motivation behavior.

Essentially, the model illustrates a system of conditional relationships in which the influence of career growth opportunity and perceived supervisor support on prosocial motivation behavior is amplified by high positive affectivity and enriched task characteristics, elucidating how perceived organizational investments elicit reciprocal prosocial actions under favorable individual and contextual conditions consistent with the exchange-based logic of SET. Despite the recognition of these relationships, there is limited understanding of how positive affectivity and task characteristics modulate the connections between career growth opportunity, perceived supervisor support, and prosocial motivation behaviors among nurses, particularly in a neglected context such as Sub-Saharan Africa (e.g., Nigeria), representing a significant gap in the organizational behavior literature.

This gap raises critical questions: How do positive emotions (positive affectivity) and task characteristics interact to influence career trajectories and supervisor support in prosocial motivation behaviors? What role does this interaction play in fostering prosocial motivation behavior in high-stress environments? Addressing these questions holds the potential to contribute to both theoretical frameworks and practical interventions aimed at enhancing worker morale and organizational efficiency. Based on this premise, the following hypotheses was posited:

- 1) Career growth opportunity is significantly associated with motivational prosocial behavior.
- 2) High perceived supervisor support have a significant association with motivational prosocial behaviour.
- 3) Positive affectivity is significantly associated with motivational prosocial behavior.
- 4) Task characteristics have a significant association with motivational prosocial behaviour.
- 5a) Positive affectivity moderates the relationship between career growth opportunity and motivational prosocial behavior such that the positive relationship between career growth opportunities and motivational prosocial behavior will be stronger for frontline workers with high positive affectivity.
- 5b) Positive affectivity moderates the relationship between perceived supervisor support and motivational prosocial behavior such that the positive relationship between perceived supervisor support and motivational prosocial behavior will be stronger for frontline workers with high positive affectivity.
- 6a) Task characteristics moderate the relationship between career growth opportunity perceived supervisor support and motivational prosocial behavior such that the positive relationship between career growth opportunity and motivational prosocial behavior will be stronger for frontline workers with high task characteristics.
- 6b) Task characteristics moderate the relationship between perceived supervisor support and motivational prosocial behavior such that the positive relationship between perceived supervisor support and motivational prosocial behavior will be stronger for frontline workers with high task characteristics.

Fig 1: Hypothesized model of the linkages among the study variables

METHODS

Study Design and Setting

The study adopted a multicenter cross-sectional hospital-based design, which was conducted between March and June 2025 among registered nurses in the southeast states, Nigeria.

Participants

The participants comprised 750 registered nurses drawn from federal government-owned hospitals in southeastern Nigeria. The demographic composition was 635 females (84.7%) and 115 males (15.3%), with ages ranging from 29 to 55 years (mean age = 35.17 years, SD = 7.48 years).

The inclusion criteria stipulated that participants must be registered nurses between the ages of ≥ 29 and ≤ 55 years, must be registered nurses with National Association of Nigeria Nurses and Midwives (NANNM), and must be full-time staff members of the sampled hospital in southeast Nigeria; consequently, only those individuals who self-reported an age within this specified range were recruited. The exclusion criteria were student nurses who had not yet qualified as registered nurses, community health extension workers, and nurses between the ages of < 29 and > 55 years.

Measures

Career Growth Scale (CGS): The Revised Career Growth Scale (CGS; Weng & McElory 2012) is a 15-item instrument designed to assess employees' perceptions of career development opportunities within their current organization. It encompasses three dimensions:

career goal progress, professional development, and promotion speed. Sample items include: “the current job motivates me to continuously acquire new knowledge about work” “my present job moves me closer to my career goals”, “My present job is relevant to my career goals and vocational growth” and “My present job sets the foundation for the realization of my career goals.” Items are rated on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 7 (Strongly Agree). A high score indicated a high perception of career growth opportunities. Weng and McElory (2012) reported an internal consistency index of 0.93. This scale has demonstrated robust internal consistency in similar study (Bai & Liu, 2018). The reliability statistics for the current study was ($\alpha = 0.827$), indicating good internal consistency.

Perceived Supervisor Support (PSSS): Perceived Supervisor Support scale (SPSS; Saks, 2006) is a 4-item instrument designed to measure employees' perceptions of the extent to which their supervisors value their contributions and care about their well-being. Sample items include; “My supervisor cares about my opinions” “My work supervisor really cares about my well-being” “My supervisor strongly considers my goals and values” and “My supervisor shows very little concern for me (R). A high score indicates favorable or cordial relationship between employees and supervisors. All items were rated from 1= never to 7= always. Items are rated on a 7-point Likert scale from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 7 (Strongly Agree). Saks (2006) reported reliability coefficient of 0.732. This scale has demonstrated robust internal consistency in similar study (Khan et al., 2015). The reliability index for the current study was ($\alpha = 0.712$), indicating good internal consistency.

Positive and Negative Affect Schedule – Short Form (PANAS-SF): The Positive and Negative Affect Schedule – Short Form (Watson et al., 1988) is a concise 20-item self-report measure designed to assess the extent to which individuals experience positive affect (PA) and negative affect (NA). Ten items that measured positive affect were used in this study because the study focused only on positive affectivity. Sample items include a number of words that describe different positive affectivity feelings and emotions such as “Interested,” “Excited” and “Strong.” It is rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (very slightly or not at all) to 5 (extremely), indicating the extent to which the respondent generally felt that way. A higher score indicates a higher experience and expression of positive emotions. Watson et al. (1988) reported an internal consistency reliability exceeding 0.70 for positive affectivity. This scale has demonstrated robust internal consistency in similar study for positive affectivity (Hovmand et al., 2023). The reliability index for the current study was ($\alpha = 0.783$), indicating good internal consistency.

Job Diagnostic Survey (JDS): The Job Diagnostic Survey JDS (Hackman & Oldham, 1975) is a 15-item scale that measures the motivational potential of jobs based on core job characteristics. It evaluates five key dimensions: Skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, and feedback. Sample items include: The job requires me to use a number of complex or high-level skills”, “The results of my work are likely to significantly affect the lives or well-being of other people, “and “The job gives me considerable opportunity for independence and freedom in how I do the work”. Items 1, 3, 5, 6, 8, 10, 12, and 14 are directly scored, whereas items 2, 4, 7, 9, 11, 13, and 15 are inversely scored. Respondents rated various aspects of their jobs on a 7-point scale ranging from 1 (very inaccurate) to 7 (very accurate). A high score indicated versatility in skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, and feedback. However, high task characteristics are indicative of high scores on the JDS scale, which are correlated with increased motivation for prosocial motivation behaviour. Hackman and Oldham (1975) reported a reliability coefficient ranging from 0.67 to 0.86 across its

subscales and overall score of 0.86. In the current study, the researchers reported reliability coefficient ranging from 0.71 to 0.85 with an overall reliability coefficients of 0.89 from the pilot study, which was conducted to provide evidence of construct validation of the scale adoption, indicating good internal consistency. Extant studies, Charambous et al. (2013) and Van Valkengoed et al. (2022) has used the measure as a unidimensional scale as applied in the current study.

Prosocial Motivation Behaviour Scale: The Prosocial Motivation Scale (Grant & Sumanth, 2009) is a 5-item scale that assesses the degree to which individuals are motivated to benefit from others through their work or a course of action. Sample items included, "I get energized by working on tasks that have the potential to benefit others", "I like to work on tasks that have the potential to benefit others," and "I prefer to work on tasks that allow me to have a positive impact on others". Respondents indicated their agreement with the statements on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 7 (Strongly Agree). A high score indicated a greater propensity for prosocial motivational behaviors. Grant and Sumanth (2009) reported reliability coefficient of 0.80. This scale has demonstrated good internal consistency in similar study (Sari & Riani, 2023). The reliability index for the current study was ($\alpha = 0.812$), indicating good internal consistency.

Procedure

This study was approved by the Ethical Review Board (blinded for review). Prior to the commencement of the study, the participants were thoroughly informed of the study objectives/requirements, and informed consent was obtained from all participants.

All procedures were conducted in accordance with the ethical standards of the responsible committee on human experimentation (institutional and national) and in compliance with the Helsinki Declaration of 1975 as amended in 2000. The study sample size was determined with a 5% margin of error, 95% confidence interval, and 50% response rate on an estimated population of 3772 registered nurses within the southeast states, as documented by the National Association of Nigeria Nurses and Midwives Membership Data 2025.

The participants were 750 of 3772 registered nurses according to the National Association of Nigeria Nurses and Midwives (NANNM) Membership Database of 2025 registered nurses in southeastern Nigeria.

The registered nurses were selected from federal government-owned hospitals to represent a comprehensive range of nursing professionals across such institutions in the five states of southeastern Nigeria. This broad representation was essential to ensure inclusivity throughout the southeast region.

The hospitals included in this study are the University of Nigeria Teaching Hospital, Ituku-Ozalla, Enugu State; the Federal Teaching Hospital, Abakaliki, Ebonyi State; the Nnamdi Azikiwe Teaching Hospital, Nnewi, Anambra State; the Federal Medical Centre, Owerri, Imo State; and the Federal Teaching Hospital, Umuahia, Abia State. Consequently, the recommended minimum sample size, calculated using the Raosoft online sample calculator (<https://www.raosoft.com/samplesize.html> (accessed on March 2025), was 349 participants.

The sample size used in this study exceeded the threshold. Previous studies have demonstrated the validity of this method in similar contexts (Ike et al., 2024; Nnadozie et al., 2025).

The Health Research Ethics Committees of these sampled hospitals granted permission for data collection. Furthermore, for data collection, Participants were recruited using convenience sampling through a web-based survey created on the Qualtrics platform.

The survey was distributed via various nursing platforms in Southeast Nigeria, including email and social media channels such as WhatsApp, Instagram, and Facebook, where they were directed to complete an anonymous survey designed to assess career growth opportunity, supervisor support, positive affectivity, task characteristics and prosocial motivation behaviours.

This methodology has been employed in previous studies (Lee et al., 2019). Participants were informed that they are free to withdraw any time from the study without being penalized and no compensation was offered for participation in the study. To minimize order effect, survey items were randomized. Standardized measures were used to measure variables under study.

Participants completed the standardized questionnaire using either computers or smartphones, depending on their internet access, with no restriction imposed on time needed to complete the survey. Upon completing the survey, participants were debriefed and given detailed information about the study prospects.

All data were anonymized at the time of collection, and responses were kept strictly confidential and used solely for research purposes. A total of 750 nurses completed the online questionnaire, which provided data that were deemed suitable for analysis. However, only participants who met the inclusion criteria were included in this study.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to test the relationship between the study variables. To test the main hypothesis, moderated regression analysis using Hayes PROCESS macro Model 2, Version 3, was used for data analysis. Prior to evaluating the quality of the constructs and models, statistical analyses were examined. Common method bias (CMB) was assessed in accordance with the recommendations of Podsakoff et al. (2024).

Following the methodology outlined by Thompson et al. (2017), variance inflation factor (VIF) values for the latent variables were estimated, all of which were below the established threshold. Furthermore, Harman's single-factor test was conducted, revealing that the variance attributable to a single factor was 36.71%, which is below the 50% threshold recommended by Podsakoff et al. (2024).

All variables were examined for adherence to the assumptions of normality and multicollinearity. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was utilized to assess the normality of the dataset, and the results indicated that the data conformed to a normal distribution.

The tolerance and VIF statistics indicated no significant multicollinearity issues among the predictors, suggesting the absence of standard bias error (Vatcheva et al. 2016) and affirming the reliability and validity of the measures.

The scale results indicated an overall acceptable model fit: $\chi^2(127) = 215.47, p < .001$; RMSEA = .07; SRMR = .053; CFI = .92; TLI = .91; IFI = .96; NFI = .92; GFI = .93; RFI = .91. According to Bentler (1990), CFI and TLI values exceeding .90, along with SRMR values below .08, denote a satisfactory to good model fit.

RESULTS

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Information

	N	%
Gender		
Male	115	15.3
Female	635	84.7
Age		
29-39	244	32.5
40-49	305	40.7
50-55	201	26.8
Marital Status		
Single	276	36.8
Married	423	56.4
Divorced	13	1.7
Widow/widower	38	5.1
Educational Qualification		
RN/RM	401	53.5
B.ScN	343	45.7
M.Sc	6	0.8
Length of service		
1-10 years	217	28.9
11-20 years	464	61.9
20 years above	69	9.2

Table 1 depicts that the demographic characteristics of the participants indicate that 15.3% were male and 84.7% were female. The average age was 35.17 ± 7.48 years old. In addition, 53.5% had RN/RM, 45.7% had B.ScN, while (0.8%) had a M.Sc. degree. For the number of years spent working, (28.9%) had spent between 1 to 10 years in service, (61.95%) had spent 11-20 years and (9.2 %) had spent 20 years and above.

Table 2: Correlations of demographic variables and statistics among the study variables

Variables	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1.Age	43.35	9.02	-								
2.Gender	-	-	-0.11	-							
3.Educational Qualification	2.33	0.71	.52**	-0.13	-						
4.Year of Experience	1.09	0.4	0.03	-0.15	0.1	-					
5.CGO	1.5	1.04	-0.1	-0.03	-0.08	.25**	-				
6.PPS	12.34	2.29	0.04	0.08	-0.01	0.03	0.04	-			
7.Positive Affectivity	40.88	3.69	-0.06	-0.11	0.12	-0.1	0.03	-0.06	-		
8.Task characteristics	76.46	8.23	-0.05	-0.04	.18*	0.03	0.02	-0.07	.20*	-	
9.PSB	23.76	3.8	.15**	-0.08	.25**	.09*	.11**	.07*	.05*	0.32	-

Note: $N = 750$, $* = p < .05$ (two-tailed), $*** = p < .01$ (two-tailed). M=Mean, SD= Standard Deviation; CCGO= Career growth opportunity; PPS= Perceived supervisor support; PSB= Prosocial motivation behaviour

Table 2 indicates that among the demographic variables added - age, gender, educational qualification, and year of experience—age ($r = 0.15$, $p < .01$), educational qualification ($r = .25$, $p < .01$), and years of experience ($r = .09$, $p < .05$) correlated with prosocial behavior. Organizational career growth ($r = .11$, $p < .05$), perceived supervisor support ($r = .07$, $p < .05$), and positive affectivity ($r = .05$, $p < .05$) were positively correlated with prosocial motivation behavior.

Table 3: Test of significance between the studied variables and prosocial behaviour using Hayes PROCESS model

Variables	β	SE	t	95%CL	
				LLCI	ULCI
Career growth opportunity	0.23	0.19	7.56**	1.46	2.47
Perceived supervisor support	0.11	0.13	4.12*	0.27	0.42
Positive affectivity	0.21	0.11	3.61**	0.38	0.45
Task characteristics	0.17	0.09	2.47*	0.17	0.29

Note: β = Regression coefficient; SE = Standard Error, * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, CL = Upper and Lower coefficient interval.

The findings from the Hayes PROCESS regression model, detailed in Table 3, provide significant insights into the direct effects of career growth opportunities, perceived supervisor support, positive affectivity, and task characteristics on prosocial behavior. Specifically, regression analysis indicated a significant positive direct relationship between organizational career growth and prosocial behavior ($\beta = 0.23$; $t = 7.56$; [95% CI = 1.46, 2.47]; ($p < 0.01$), and perceived supervisor support and prosocial behavior ($\beta = 0.11$; $t = 4.12$; [95% CI = .27, .42]; ($p < 0.01$), thereby supporting Hypotheses 1 and 2, respectively. Organizational career growth and perceived supervisor support increases by 0.23 units and 0.11 units respectively for every unit increase in organizational career growth and perceived supervisor support, according to the beta coefficient (β). This finding suggests that heightened perceptions of career growth opportunity and perceived supervisor support correlate with increased levels of prosocial behavior, underscoring the influence of career growth opportunity and perceived supervisor support on prosocial behavior among frontline workers (e.g., nurses). Additionally, the two intervening variables, positive affectivity ($\beta = 0.21$; $t = 3.61$; [95% CI = .38, .45]; ($p < .01$) and task characteristics ($\beta = 0.17$; $t = 2.47$; [95% CI = .17, .29]; ($p < .05$), exhibited distinct direct positive effects on prosocial behavior, thus supporting hypotheses 3 and 4, respectively. Positive affectivity and task characteristics increases by 0.21 units and 0.17 units respectively for every unit increase in positive affectivity and task characteristics, according to the beta coefficient (β). This indicates that increased positive affectivity and task characteristics are linked to increased levels of prosocial behavior among frontline workers.

Table 4: Test of moderation of positive affectivity and Task characteristics in the relationship between Career growth opportunity, Perceived supervisor support and prosocial motivation behaviour using Hayes PROCESS model

Variables	B	SE	t	95%CL	
				LLCI	ULCI
PA X CGO	0.15	0.27	3.57**	0.33	0.46
PA X PSS	0.03	0.21	1.57	-0.17	0.23
TC X CGO	0.09	0.17	2.63**	0.22	0.37
TC X PSS	0.11	0.07	4.23**	0.33	0.42

Note: PA= Positive Affectivity; TC=Task Characteristics; CGO= Career Growth Opportunities; PSS; Perceived Supervisor Support.

Table 4 shows that the interaction effect between positive affectivity and organizational career growth on prosocial behavior was significant ($\beta = .15$; $t = 3.57$; [95% CI = .33, .46]; $p < .01$), thereby supporting Hypothesis 5a. This finding indicates that positive affectivity strengthens the positive relationship between organizational career growth and prosocial behavior, suggesting that positive affectivity influences prosocial behavior. The slope of the

interaction (see Figure 2) shows that organizational career growth was not significantly related to prosocial behavior for individuals with low positive affectivity ($\beta = -2.31, p > .05$) but was positively and significantly related to those with moderate positive affectivity ($\beta = 2.43, p < .01$) and high positive affectivity ($\beta = 3.69, p < .01$).

Figure 2: Interaction slope showing the moderating role of positive affectivity in the relationship between career growth opportunities and prosocial motivational behavior

However, the interaction effect between positive affectivity and perceived supervisor support on prosocial behavior was not significant ($\beta = .03; t = 1.57; [95\% \text{ CI} = -.17, .23]$); thus, Hypothesis 5b was not supported. This indicates that positive affectivity did not moderate the relationship between perceived supervisor support and prosocial behavior.

Figure 3: Interaction slope showing moderating role of task characteristics in the relationship between organizational career growth and prosocial behaviour

Furthermore, the interaction effect between task characteristics and organizational career growth on prosocial behavior was significant ($\beta = .11; t = 2.35; [95\% \text{ CI} = .27, .41]; p < 0.01$), thus supporting Hypothesis 6a. This result suggests that task characteristics strengthen the positive relationship between organizational career growth and prosocial behavior, indicating

that task characteristics moderate this relationship. The slope of the interaction (see Figure 3) revealed that organizational career growth was not related to prosocial behavior for those with low task characteristics ($\beta = 0.19, p < .05$) but for those with moderate ($\beta = 0.24, p < .01$) and high task characteristics ($\beta = 0.33, p < .01$).

However, the interaction effect between task characteristics and perceived supervisor support on prosocial behavior was significant ($\beta = .11; t = 4.23; [95\% \text{ CI} = .33, .42]; p < 0.01$), thus supporting Hypothesis 6b. This result suggests that task characteristics strengthens the positive relationship between perceived supervisor support and prosocial behaviour, indicating that task characteristics created an influence on prosocial behaviour. The slope of the interaction shown in (Figure 4) indicates that task characteristics were not significantly related to prosocial behaviour for individuals with low perceived supervisor support ($\beta = 0.24, p > .05$), but were significantly related for those with moderate ($\beta = 0.33, p < .01$) and high ($\beta = 0.44, p < .01$) levels of perceived supervisor support. The R^2 for the model was .32, indicating that these variables accounted for 32% of the variance in prosocial behavior, which was found to be significant: $R^2 = .32, F(4, 263) = 9.08, p < .01$.

Figure 4: Interaction slope showing moderating role of task characteristics in the relationship between perceived supervisor support and prosocial motivation behaviour

DISCUSSION

The findings of the present study offer valuable insights into the complex interplay between organizational career growth opportunities, perceived supervisor support, positive affectivity, and task characteristics in influencing prosocial motivation behavior among frontline workers, particularly nurses in sub-Saharan Africa. First, the research indicates a significant relationship between organizational career growth opportunities and prosocial motivational behavior. Specifically, the results suggest that perceived organizational career growth stimulates prosocial motivational behavior among workers. This finding is consistent with the existing literature (e.g., Weer & Greenhaus, 2020), which demonstrates that increased organizational career growth opportunities facilitate prosocial motivational behavior. In alignment with this perspective, Okurame (2012) asserts that career growth opportunities are

not merely beneficial; they are essential for promoting prosocial behavior among frontline workers, such as nurses. This is significant because career growth opportunities serve as crucial catalysts for enhancing motivation, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment (Spagnoli, 2020). For instance, when nurses perceive clear pathways for advancement and development, they feel valued and empowered, fostering a stronger sense of responsibility and increased willingness to support others. According to Zhu and Song (2022), such opportunities are instrumental in mitigating burnout, enhancing psychological well-being, and cultivating positive professional identity. This is pertinent because these factors are essential in encouraging behaviors, such as empathy, cooperation, and exceeding formal job duties. Consequently, nurses are more inclined to engage in supportive behaviors toward patients and colleagues. Furthermore, the correlation between organizational career growth and prosocial behavior is particularly pronounced among frontline workers. This is evident because this relationship is firmly grounded in Social Exchange Theory, which posits that when employees recognize opportunities for career advancement, skill development, and recognition within an organization, they are more likely to reciprocate through positive, voluntary actions that benefit others, known as prosocial behaviors (Snippe et al., 2017). This aligns with Wickramasinghe and Premachandra (2021) assertion that career growth is a cornerstone of organizational support, self-efficacy, and job satisfaction, which in turn amplifies individuals' willingness to exceed formal job responsibilities, assists colleagues, contributes to team goals, and upholds ethical standards. Similarly, Vande-Griek et al. (2020) asserts that investments in employee development not only elevate individual motivation, but also cultivate a more collaborative and socially responsible workplace culture, where discretionary behaviors are exhibited.

As anticipated, perceived supervisor support emerged as a significant catalyst for enhancing prosocial behavior among employees. This finding suggests that increased perceived supervisor support is associated with elevated levels of prosocial motivational behavior. This observation aligns with previous research (e.g., Haynie et al., 2022), which indicates that support from significant figures (e.g., supervisors) fosters employees' reciprocity of perceived support with positive discretionary behaviors. This is evident because perceived supervisor support fosters a sense of belonging, trust, and psychological safety, which encourages individuals to exceed their formal roles in assisting others, resolving conflicts, or contributing to team cohesion (Contreras et al., 2020). For instance, when employees perceive that their supervisors genuinely value their contributions and prioritize their well-being, they are more likely to surpass their formal job responsibilities and actively assist their colleagues. According to Trombini et al. (2025), this support fosters an environment characterized by psychological safety, trust, and strong organizational commitment, which in turn promotes prosocial behaviors such as cooperation, altruism, and helping behaviors. Moreover, the strength of this relationship is further enhanced by factors such as job satisfaction, affective commitment, and organizational identification. In essence, supervisors who provide both emotional and instrumental support do not merely foster a positive work environment; rather, they cultivate a culture of voluntary, helpful behaviors that significantly benefits both co-workers and the organization as a whole. Thus, supportive supervisors are fundamental to a thriving and collaborative workplace characterized by the exhibition of discretionary behaviors from organizational members.

Furthermore, positive affectivity exerts a significant positive influence on prosocial motivational behavior. This finding aligns with previous research (e.g., Gregghel et al., 2020), which suggests that employees experiencing positive emotions, such as enthusiasm, energy, and joy, are more inclined to engage in behaviors that benefit others, including helping, sharing,

or cooperating. According to Fredrickson and Brainigan (2005), positive emotions expand individuals' thought–action repertoires, enhance their openness to others' needs, and foster empathy and social connectedness. The findings indicate that employees with elevated levels of positive affectivity tend to exhibit stronger prosocial motivation driven by a genuine desire to assist colleagues and contribute to the collective good (Feng et al., 2021). This is significant because positive affectivity denotes an inherent propensity to experience uplifting emotions such as enthusiasm, alertness, and joy, which ignite discretionary behaviors. For instance, individuals exhibiting positive affect are not only more inclined, but also intrinsically motivated to engage in actions that benefit others, including helping, sharing, and cooperating. This significant relationship was effectively elucidated by the broaden-and-build theory of positive emotions, which posits that positive affect considerably enhances attention and cognitive processes (Fredrickson, 2001). Consequently, such enhancement renders them more perceptive to the needs of others and is naturally predisposed to compassion. Similarly, empirical evidence (e.g., George, 1991) strongly supports that individuals with heightened levels of positive affect demonstrate increased empathy, social connectivity, and a strong motivation to sustain interpersonal harmony. Invariably, these characteristics substantially contribute to a notable increase in prosocial behaviors across various contexts, which is essential for cultivating a more compassionate and cooperative society.

In addition, the findings of the present study revealed a positive association between task characteristics and prosocial motivational behavior. This suggests that employees who perceive their tasks as meaningful and impactful, particularly in ways that positively affect others, are more inclined to engage in behaviors that exceed formal job requirements such as assisting coworkers and contributing to the organization. This observation aligns with the findings of Cotic et al. (2025) and Bolino and Grant (2016), which reported that task characteristics, such as task significance, autonomy, skill variety, task identity, and feedback, are critical in fostering prosocial motivation behavior in the workplace. Consistent with this, Tood and Kent (2016) asserts that these elements stimulate employees' propensity to engage in prosocial behaviors, including assisting colleagues, collaborating effectively, and surpassing formal job expectations. For instance, when employees perceive their tasks to be meaningful and impactful, they develop a profound sense of responsibility and empathy, which naturally leads to prosocial actions. Similarly, autonomy enables workers to make independent decisions, enhance their sense of ownership, and motivate them to engage in voluntary helpful behaviors. Skill variety and feedback serve as powerful motivators that enhance intrinsic motivation, which is directly linked to increased cooperation and altruism. Notably, enriching task design is not only beneficial for skill mastery but is also essential for cultivating a work environment that thrives on prosocial conduct (Carlo et al., 2019).

As expected, positive affectivity significantly moderated the relationship between organizational career growth opportunities and prosocial motivational behavior. This indicates that positive affectivity enhances the connection between organizational career growth and prosocial behavior, thereby increasing employees' propensity to engage in cooperative and helpful actions. This finding aligns with previous research (e.g. George, 1991; Naragon-Gainey & Watson, 2019), which demonstrates that organizational career growth encompasses the availability of advancement, skill development, and long-term career prospects within the workplace, all of which can inspire employees to engage in behaviors that benefit both others and the organization. However, the extent to which these opportunities foster prosocial motivation is contingent on individual differences in affective dispositions. For instance, employees with high positive affectivity (i.e., those who typically experience positive

emotions, such as enthusiasm, joy, and optimism) are more inclined to perceive career growth signals as meaningful and encouraging. This positive emotional outlook enhances their intrinsic motivation to contribute positively to their work environment, often by helping others, volunteering for additional tasks, or cooperating with team members (Gherghel et al., 2020). Conversely, employees with low positive affectivity may not strongly internalize organizational growth opportunity prospects, resulting in lower levels of prosocial motivation. Thus, positive affectivity functions as a psychological amplifier, augmenting the motivational impact of career growth opportunities on prosocial behavior (Fredrickson & Branigan, 2015). Individuals with high positive affectivity—those who consistently exhibit optimism, enthusiasm, and energy—are far more adept at converting career advancement opportunities into prosocial behaviors such as assisting colleagues and exceeding formal job responsibilities. Conversely, those with lower levels of positive affectivity showed markedly diminished prosocial responses to identical career growth signals. This compelling evidence underscores that the motivational and emotional resources inherent in positive affectivity substantially magnify the advantageous effects of perceived career development on employees' interpersonal and citizenship behaviors. Naragon-Gainey and Watson (2019) emphasized that embracing and fostering positive affectivity within the workforce is not merely beneficial; it is essential to maximize the potential for career growth opportunities to cultivate a thriving cooperative organizational environment.

Contrary to expectations, the anticipated moderating effect of positive affectivity on the relationship between perceived supervisor support (PSS) and prosocial motivational behavior is absent, which can be attributed to several theoretical and contextual factors. First, perceived supervisor support functions as a significant situational predictor of prosocial motivation, and its effects may be sufficiently robust, thereby limiting the explanatory value of additional dispositional influences such as positive affectivity. This suggests a potential ceiling effect, wherein supervisor support sufficiently drives prosocial behavior regardless of employees' emotional dispositions (Haynie et al., 2022). However, the findings of this study diverge from previous research (e.g., Barik et al., 2025; Contreras et al., 2020; Yoon & Thye, 2000; Zhu et al., 2024), which demonstrated the proximal influence of positive affectivity on perceived supervisor support (PSS) and prosocial motivational behavior. These inconsistencies may be attributed to the incongruence between the trait-like nature of positive affectivity and the situational character of PSS, which may constrain meaningful interaction effects. Although individuals with high positive affectivity generally exhibit greater prosocial tendencies (George, 1991), their responses to supervisor support may not significantly differ from those with low positive affectivity. Furthermore, in dynamic, risk-prone, operational, and service-oriented environments or contexts such as those prevalent among frontline workers, employees may prioritize external cues such as supervisor behavior over internal states when engaging in helping behaviors (Barik et al., 2025; Haynie et al., 2022; Taylor et al., 2018). These factors suggest that while perceived supervisor support and positive affectivity independently contribute to prosocial motivation, their interactions may not be statistically or practically significant in this context.

However, task characteristics moderated the relationship between organizational career growth opportunities and prosocial motivational behavior. This finding indicates that task characteristics enhance the positive relationship between organizational career growth opportunities and prosocial motivation behavior among frontline workers such as nurses. These findings are consistent with those of previous studies (e.g., Ni & Hung, 2025; Ohly & Fritz, 2010; Permata & Mangundjaya, 2021), which suggest that, for organizations to fully capitalize

on the benefits of career development in promoting prosocial motivation, they must ensure that job designs incorporate meaningful and engaging task characteristics. Specifically, when tasks are perceived as high in autonomy, significance, and skill variety, the positive effect of career growth opportunities on prosocial motivation is amplified. In such enriching task environments, employees are more likely to perceive organizational support for career advancement as a sign of value and trust, which in turn fosters a stronger desire to help others and contribute positively to the workplace. Evidently, task characteristics are crucial for enhancing the positive effects of career growth opportunities on prosocial behavior among frontline workers (Kim et al., 2015). For instance, when task characteristics such as autonomy, task significance, skill variety, and feedback are heightened, the relationship between perceived career growth opportunities and prosocial behavior is significantly strengthened. Thus, in dynamic work environments, where tasks are meaningful, complex, or encourage personal initiative, employees who perceive greater career advancement prospects are more likely to engage in helping behaviors, cooperation, and other prosocial actions. (Carlo et al., 2019). Conversely, when task characteristics are deficient, the motivational impact of career growth opportunities on prosocial behavior is notably diminished. Hence, this compelling evidence highlights the necessity of enriching work tasks to maximize the beneficial effects of career development prospects on employees' willingness to support colleagues in the workplace.

Similarly, task characteristics moderated the relationship between perceived supervisor support and prosocial motivational behavior. This finding indicates that task characteristics enhance the positive relationship between perceived supervisor support and prosocial motivational behavior among frontline workers. This result aligns with previous research (e.g., Grant, 2008; Hatcher et al., 1989; Hayine et al., 2022), which demonstrated that high task characteristics, such as autonomy, task significance, variety, and feedback, foster the positive effects of perceived supervisor support on prosocial motivation. This is significant because, in enriched task environments, employees are more likely to perceive supervisor support and career development initiatives as meaningful and empowering, thereby increasing their willingness to engage in behaviors that benefit others in the workplace (Ramamoorthy & Flood, 2004). Conversely, under conditions of low task characteristics, even high levels of perceived supervisor support and organizational career growth opportunities may fail to fully translate into prosocial motivation because of a lack of stimulating and intrinsically motivating work. This may lead employees to feel constrained or disconnected from the broader impact of their work, which severely undermines their motivation to reciprocate supportive leadership through helping behaviors (Chaine et al., 2023). Thus, task characteristics play a critical role in enhancing the motivational pathways through which organizational and supervisory support mechanisms influence prosocial employee behavior (Chiaburu et al., 2014). Therefore, the motivational potential inherent in a task is a crucial determinant of how supervisor support translates into prosocial outcomes.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The findings of this study offer significant theoretical, practical, and policy implications. Theoretically, this study reinforces the social exchange framework by demonstrating that frontline workers are more inclined to engage in prosocial behavior when they perceive opportunities for career advancement and receive supportive supervision, particularly when these factors are moderated by positive affectivity and enriching task characteristics. This

underscores the dual influence of individual emotional traits and job design in shaping employee behavior.

Practically, the findings suggest that organizations should invest in career development, provide supportive supervision, and consider both the emotional disposition of workers and the structure of their tasks to enhance prosocial outcomes. For example, emotionally intelligent management and well-designed roles can optimize the benefits of organizational support. This is pertinent because recognizing the potential of prosocial behavior in the career development of frontline workers (e.g., nurses), is essential for transformative management practices.

At the policy level, the study highlights the necessity for workforce development programs that include supervisor training, job enrichment strategies, and psychological well-being initiatives, especially in frontline sectors, where such factors critically impact performance, engagement, and retention. This is pertinent, because perceived supervisor support serves as a potent catalyst for increasing employees' positive affectivity, thereby effectively mitigating task-related stressors. By fostering a workplace culture that emphasizes fairness and actively acknowledges employees' contributions, organizations can effectively counteract negative perceptions of unfairness. Such a strategic approach not only enhances employee morale but also contributes to organizational success.

Furthermore, insights from this study suggest that illegitimate tasks can adversely affect organizational prosocial behavior through the mediation of negative affectivity. This suggests that management practices should prioritize task characteristics that enhance rather than hinder employee performance. Consequently, this will help in implementation of strategies that integrate career development opportunities with supportive supervisory relationships, which is essential to cultivate an engaged workforce. This dual approach not only enhances employees' career trajectories, but also bolsters their inclination towards prosocial behavior, which benefits organizational dynamics and service delivery.

In addition, the findings of this study provide valuable insights into knowledge-driven strategies that can facilitate the development of functional models to enhance workers' motivation and engagement. This in turn contributes to improved service quality and customer loyalty. Consequently, these implications extend beyond individual well-being, indicating transformative potential for workplace dynamics and organizational success.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

While this study offers valuable insights into the interplay between career growth opportunities, perceived supervisor support, and prosocial behavior among frontline workers, several limitations warrant consideration. First, the cross-sectional research design restricts causal inferences as it captures relationships at a single point in time without accounting for temporal variations. Future studies should adopt a longitudinal study in order to help explain any mixed variation that were not established. Second, reliance on self-reported measures may introduce common method bias and social desirability effects, potentially compromising the objectivity of responses, although, the possibility of common bias error was mitigated through confidentiality and anonymity in the participants' responses. Third, the sample was limited to frontline workers within a specific context (nurses), which may constrain the generalizability of the findings to other occupational groups and sectors. Future studies should consider expanding the scope of the participants to include other frontline professionals to broaden the generalizability of the findings. Furthermore, the study focused exclusively on positive

affectivity and task characteristics as moderators, omitting other potentially influential variables, such as organizational culture, leadership style, and job stress. Future studies should incorporate these variables of interest to explore their effects on the antecedent and outcome variables.

CONCLUSION

This study investigates the influence of career growth opportunities and perceived supervisor support on prosocial behavior among frontline workers, while examining the moderating roles of positive affectivity and task characteristics. The results demonstrate that both career growth opportunities and supervisor support significantly enhance prosocial behavior, highlighting their importance in promoting positive interpersonal actions within the workplace. Task characteristics were identified as moderators in these relationships, indicating that the nature of work itself can either amplify or diminish the impact of organizational support on prosocial outcomes. Conversely, positive affectivity did not significantly moderate all relationships, suggesting that its role may be more complex or context dependent. Overall, this study underscores the critical role of supportive work environments and enriching job designs in fostering prosocial behavior among frontline workers (e.g., nurses), with implications for management practices aimed at enhancing organizational effectiveness and employee well-being. The findings indicate that career growth opportunities and supervisor support are not universally effective; their impact on prosocial behavior is contingent upon the emotional disposition of workers (positive affectivity) and the nature of their tasks. These insights are essential for tailoring human resource strategies to enhance morale, productivity, and service outcomes in frontline sectors.

Authors' contributions

OOI: Conceptualization, project administration, resources, validation, software, methodology, writing of the original draft, review and editing. OGI: Conceptualization, project administration, review and editing. EEN: Supervision, project administration, review and editing. COAA: Supervision, project administration, review and editing.

Data availability statement

The datasets generated and analysed during the current study will be available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no known conflicts of interest.

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Ethical Approval

The study was approved by the Ethical Review Board, Department of Psychology, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. All procedures followed were under the ethical standards of the responsible committee on human experimentation (institutional and national) and with the Helsinki Declaration of 1975, as revised in 2013.

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